

The determination of a celestial coordinate system (Option A)

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The original aim of this note (which is a summary and revision of some previous notes) was a discussion of the limiting accuracy of the desired astrometric data that can be achieved assuming that photon noise is the dominating source of error for the majority of stars. However, as it was written, the feeling emerged that error estimates, even within a factor of two, cannot be made with any certainty at this stage of the project. This is, of course, rather unsatisfactory since the scientific value and potentialities of an astrometric satellite can be discussed only in relation to its expected performances. Hence, without any intention to anticipate any part of the detailed software study to be carried out, I have tried to sketch a possible scheme for the reductions in Option A, with the purpose of getting a firmer basis for preliminary estimates of accuracies. Perhaps it may also be of some help in our discussions if we can form a good picture of how the reductions possibly can be carried out and what demands for computing time etc. there will be.

Most of the data and mathematical details are concentrated in three Appendices:

1. A three-step procedure for deriving the astrometric parameters from great-circle scans
2. A simplified error propagation model
3. The computing efforts for the reductions of an RS system

The following is a summary of the results.

The characteristic feature of Option A is that angles between pairs of stars are measured only along, and not perpendicular to, a great circle approximately coinciding with the strip on the sky being scanned during one or a few successive orbits. A closed chain of angle measurements along this reference great circle makes possible a calibration of the basic angle, the scale at the grid, and the orientation and tilt of the grid. Thus, each successfully completed orbit with a closed chain of angle measurements constitutes a basic set of observations which will always contribute to the determination of the celestial sphere, independent of whether other orbits come off well.

Because of this it is both intuitively natural and mathematically convenient to split the reductional procedure into the following three steps: 1. We consider one or a few consecutive orbits as a unit and solve for the basic angle etc. and for the angles of the stars along

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the reference great circle. An arbitrary zero-point for the angles is chosen. 2. Combination of all step 1 solutions allows elimination of all stellar positions, proper motions, and parallaxes, and we can solve for the zero-points of the reference great circles in a consistent, but provisional, system of celestial coordinates. 3. By combining solutions from step 1 and 2 for a particular star, its astrometric unknowns are very easily computed.

The astrometric data in the provisional system chosen during step 2 are later to be transformed into a more definite (inertial) system, when the motions of quasars, radio stars, etc. in the provisional system have been studied.

The error propagation model in Appendix 2 gives error estimates less optimistic than in the MDS Report, but approximately consistent with those given by Hög (17.12.76). However, the error propagation through step 2 has so far never been studied. Strictly speaking, this means that it has not been demonstrated that the proposed configuration permits a resolution of the astrometric unknowns.

The computing times for some critical parts of the reductions have been estimated (Appendix 3). A system with 40 000 RS stars involves 200 000 unknowns and 15 million angle measurements, but the indications are that a large computer is able to make a solution in a few hours without excessive demands for internal or external storage capacity.

Appendix 1.

A three-step procedure for deriving positions, proper motions, and parallaxes of stars observed by scanning great circles (Option A)

The building up of a celestial sphere by means of a system of RS stars, about one per square degree, means that we have a problem involving about 200 000 unknowns and 15 millions angle measurements. It is certainly necessary to break down the problem into manageable pieces; fortunately this can be done without imposing too many basically unnecessary assumptions. The reductions are split into three steps as follows:

1. For a number of consecutive orbits (from here on called a group) we introduce a reference great circle, with its pole and zero-point arbitrarily chosen but fixed among the stars. The pole should, however, be close to the average position of the rotation axis. For all stars observed during these orbits we solve for their angles (v_i) along this circle, and we also obtain determinations of the basic angle, the scale value on the grid, and the orientation and tilt of the grid. Two basic assumptions are involved here. One is that the positions of the stars perpendicular to the great circle and similarly of the two optical axes of the instrument are sufficiently accurately known (within $\sim 0.2^\circ$), so that when projected onto the great circle they produce insignificant errors in the positions along this circle. The other is that a number of quantities are constant during this group of orbits, for instance the basic angle, but also proper motions are neglected.
2. Combining all groups for the entire period of observation (2.5 years), it is possible to eliminate the astrometric unknowns of all stars, leaving us with a system of equations for the zero-points of all the groups in a consistent (but provisional) system of coordinates on the celestial sphere.
3. By combination of the solutions in step 1 and 2 for all observations of a specific star, it is a trivial matter to set up and solve the normal equations for the five astrometric unknowns of that star. This process is repeated for all the stars.

Step 1

As an illustration only, I give the approximate form of the equation of condition for one connexion (angle measurement) between two stars denoted 1 and 2. The equation is linearized assuming central (gnomonic) projection. The coordinates of the stars in the grid system are (y_1, z_1) and (y_2, z_2) , the y-axis being approximately in the scanning direction (cf. Figure 2 in DP/PS(76)11).

$$\begin{aligned} (v_1 - v_2)_{\text{observed}} - (v_1 - v_2)_{\text{computed}} = \\ = dv_1 - dv_2 + de_1 + (y_1 - y_2)de_2 + (z_1 - z_2)de_3 + \\ + (y_1^2 + y_2^2)de_4 + (y_1z_1 - y_2z_2)de_5 + (z_1 + z_2)\tan \frac{1}{2}|v_1 - v_2| \cdot de_6 \end{aligned}$$

dv_i is the correction to the computed v_i , de_1 is the correction to the basic angle (this term is deleted if both stars belong to the same field); de_2 is related to the scale value, de_3 to the grid orientation; de_4 and de_5 give the tilt of the grid and de_6 the zero-point in z direction. When forming the normal equations we settle the zero-point of the angles v_i by means of the equation $\sum_i dv_i = 0$, and add the corresponding Lagrangean multiplier to the list of unknowns.

Step 2

We number the groups $j = 1, 2, \dots, J$ and we have to find J zero-points b_j . Let us number the observations $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$. 'Observation no. k' now means a value of dv_i obtained in step 1 for a star (i) observed within group no. j. i and j are regarded as functions of k, and an observation is denoted dv_k to distinguish it from other observations of the same star. The k:th equation of condition is

$$\bar{P}_k \bar{R}_i^t + b_j(k) = dv_k,$$

where $\bar{R}_i^t = (\Delta\lambda \cos \beta, \Delta\beta, \mu_\lambda \cos \beta, \mu_\beta, \pi)_i$ is the vector with the astrometric unknowns for star no. i, and

$$\bar{P}_k = (-\sin \eta, -\cos \eta, -\tau \sin \eta, -\tau \cos \eta,$$

$$R(\sin(\lambda - \lambda_0)\sin \eta + \sin \beta \cos(\lambda - \lambda_0)\cos \eta)).$$

η is the angle between the reference great circle near the star and the arc $\lambda = \text{constant}$. τ is the epoch.

The set of K such equations is concisely written in matrix form as

$$\underline{P} \underline{R} + \underline{Q} \underline{B} = \underline{D}, \quad (\text{A1.4})$$

where the elements of the matrices are ($\delta_{i,j}$ is the Kronecker delta)

$$\begin{aligned} P_{ki} &= \delta_{i,i(k)} \bar{P}_k, & R_{i1} &= \bar{R}_i^t, \\ Q_{kj} &= \delta_{j,j(k)}, & B_{j1} &= b_j, & D_{k1} &= dv_k. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A1.5})$$

The normal equations become

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{P}^t \underline{P} \underline{R} + \underline{P}^t \underline{Q} \underline{B} &= \underline{P}^t \underline{D}, \\ \underline{Q}^t \underline{P} \underline{R} + \underline{Q}^t \underline{Q} \underline{B} &= \underline{Q}^t \underline{D}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A1.6})$$

Both $\underline{P}^t \underline{P}$ and $\underline{Q}^t \underline{Q}$ are diagonal matrices and hence easily inverted. The diagonal elements of $\underline{P}^t \underline{P}$ are 5×5 matrices and the j :th diagonal element of $\underline{Q}^t \underline{Q}$ is the number of stars in group no. j .

Elimination of $\underline{R}$ between the two equations in (A1.6) results in

$$(\underline{Q}^t \underline{Q} - \underline{Q}^t \underline{P} (\underline{P}^t \underline{P})^{-1} \underline{P}^t \underline{Q}) \underline{B} = \underline{Q}^t \underline{D} - \underline{Q}^t \underline{P} (\underline{P}^t \underline{P})^{-1} \underline{P}^t \underline{D}. \quad (\text{A1.7})$$

The matrix $\underline{T} = \underline{Q}^t \underline{Q} - \underline{Q}^t \underline{P} (\underline{P}^t \underline{P})^{-1} \underline{P}^t \underline{Q}$ is a symmetric $J \times J$ matrix of rank $\leq J - 6$. The six degrees of freedom correspond to the phases and angular velocities for the rotation of the system around three axes. In order to solve the system (A1.7) we have to decide on the provisional celestial coordinate system to be used. One way is to specify certain astrometric data for a few stars. Another is to use the pseudo-inverse of $\underline{T}$, which gives a solution for which $\sum_j b_j^2 = \text{minimum}$, i.e., we get an over-all fit to the system used for the input coordinates (e.g. AGK3/SRS). This provisional system is later transformed into any desired (inertial) system.

Step 3

When $\underline{B}$ is known we finally obtain the vector $\underline{R}$ (containing the astrometric parameters) from

$$\underline{R} = (\underline{P}^t \underline{P})^{-1} \underline{P}^t (\underline{D} - \underline{Q} \underline{B}). \quad (\text{A1.8})$$

Appendix 2.

A simplified error propagation model for Option A

The accuracies of the astrometric parameters (positions, proper motions, and parallaxes) have been estimated in the Mission Definition Study Report and in a note prepared by Dr. Hög (Tables 5 and 6). However, the value and possible weaknesses of the estimates are perhaps better appreciated when the underlying error propagation model is formulated. The following model is based on the three-step procedure outlined in Appendix 1.

In step 1 we derive for a particular star (identified by subscript i) an angle v_i along the reference great circle, the zero-point of which is arbitrarily chosen. Let σ be the mean error of a measurement of the distance $y_2 - y_1$ between two stellar images in the grid system. The mean error of v_i is given by

$$\sigma_v^2 = V \sigma^2, \quad (\text{A2.1})$$

in which the variance V (assumed to be nearly the same for all stars) depends on the density of stars, the size of the field, the basic angle, the number (m) of consecutive orbits treated together in step 1, etc.

The angle b_j of the zero-point of the j :th reference great circle relative to the provisional celestial coordinate system is found during step 2. Hence, the angle of star no. i as measured along this circle and referred to the provisional system is $w_{ij} = b_j + v_i$. For the mean error of w_{ij} we assume

$$\sigma_w^2 = \sigma_b^2 + \sigma_v^2. \quad (\text{A2.2a})$$

This formula is valid for a relatively bright and well observed RS star. For a faint PS star, which does not significantly strengthen the solution for the system of RS stars, but is rather loosely attached to this system by a measurement of the distance $y_{PS} - y_{RS}$ with accuracy σ_p , we assume a mean error according to

$$\sigma_w^2 = \sigma_b^2 + \sigma_v^2 + \sigma_p^2. \quad (\text{A2.2b})$$

The 'mean error per orbit' or $m^{0.5} \sigma_w$ forms a natural basis for estimating the mean errors of the five astrometric unknowns when different scanning modes are studied. For instance, for the mean error of the parallax we put

$$\sigma_\pi^2 = P_\pi m \sigma_w^2. \quad (\text{A2.3})$$

The five variances P are easily computed for any given scheme of scanning

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the sky. They depend also on the total observing time; for any regular scanning scheme they decrease with observing time according to t^{-1} (positions and parallaxes) or t^{-3} (proper motions). A certain minimum of observing time is necessary for the five- or sixfold sky coverage needed for a separation of the five unknowns. This minimum time can be very different for different scanning schemes. Equation (A2.3) represents the error analysis associated with step 3.

It is seen that evaluating σ_{π} , for instance, requires that we know σ , σ_p , V , σ_b , and P_{π} . Let us see what we know about these quantities.

The mean errors σ and σ_p of distances between stellar images are estimated by means of Table 1 in DP/PS(76)11 (p. 12), when we know the times spent on the measurements.

In the Mission Definition Study, the variance V was estimated by means of an analogy to the general symmetric method for determination of division corrections of a meridian circle. With about 360 RS stars per orbit this gives $V \sim 0.5$. I have confirmed this figure in a more realistic simulation of step 1, which takes into account the random distribution of stars and makes a simultaneous determination of the basic angle, the scale value at the grid, and the orientation and tilt of the grid.

The mean error σ_b of the zero-point of a reference great circle has been neglected in the MDS and in the later notes by Dr. Hølg. It may be that it really is small, but I would like to emphasise that it has not been demonstrated that its contribution is negligible. The possibility of constructing a rigid sphere actually depends on how well the putting together of many scans can be made in step 2 - and this is reflected in the size of σ_b . A determination of σ_b requires the solution of a large and dense system of equations (the number of unknowns being of the order of 1500). For the moment, we have to go on neglecting this term, being aware of that we can only establish lower limits for the mean errors of the astrometric parameters.

Finally, we have the variances P . Two modes of scanning the sky are discussed in the MDS report: inclined scanning and revolving scanning. Their performances are compared in Table 6 of Dr. Hølg's notes. Other modes of scanning are likely to surpass both of these in one respect or another, but one can hardly envisage a drastic improvement of accuracy as compared to these, because all scanning schemes are subject to certain restrictions. In particular, we demand that the angle (ζ) from the sun to the rotation axis should not exceed (say) 45° , because

of the power requirement and possible problems with shielding; furthermore, we prefer that the rotation axis does not often change direction suddenly but moves smoothly and slowly enough that consecutive scans partly overlap.

Inclined scanning gives a very good resolution of the five astrometric unknowns, but it requires at least 2.5 years observation and does not cover the entire sphere.

Revolving scanning with $270^\circ/\zeta$ revolutions around the sun per year gives (as first noted by Dr. Hög) a particularly homogeneous coverage of the entire sphere under reasonable conditions (ζ about 40° ; the speed at which the rotation axis moves among the stars is $0.22 - 0.36$ per orbit almost independent of ζ , which is well compatible with the proposed field width of nearly 1°). Figure 1 gives the error-factors (square roots of the variances P) for the five astrometric unknowns as functions of ζ . Figure 1 was computed for 3.0 years of observation, but already an observing time of 1.5 years gives a good separation of the unknowns. Thus, revolving scanning is much less vulnerable than inclined scanning in the case the satellite operation or data transmission should fail for some periods. With revolving scanning we may lose up to 40% of the orbits during the satellite's lifetime of 2.5 years and still get valuable astrometric data for the whole sky; the corresponding figure for inclined scanning is almost 0%.

As an example, let us take a system of 40 000 RS stars and 100 000 PS stars, typically of magnitude 9 and 11, respectively. During one orbit we encounter 360 RS stars and 900 PS stars. Each RS star is connected to 6 other RS stars, and the time t_R (in seconds) is spent on each connexion. Each PS star is connected to only one RS star during t_P seconds. The total time spent on these connexions is

$$3 \cdot 360 \cdot t_R + 900 \cdot t_P = 0.8 \cdot 5700^S,$$

allowing 20% of available time to be used on RS stars and 45° slits. From Table 1 in DP/PS(76)11 we obtain $\sigma = 0.032 t_R^{-0.5}$ and $\sigma_P = 0.056 t_P^{-0.5}$. By means of the formulae given above (neglecting σ_b) we can minimise σ_w for a PS star with respect to t_R and t_P . This gives $t_R = 1.3^S$, $t_P = 3.5^S$, $\sigma_w(\text{RS}) = 0.020$, and $\sigma_w(\text{PS}) = 0.036$. Only 25% of the time is spent on RS-RS connexions, compared to 40% for the example in the Mission Definition Study Report. 2.5 years of observation with revolving scanning ($\zeta = 40^\circ$) gives for stars at $\beta = 45^\circ$:

	position	proper motion	parallax
RS	0.003	0.004 yr ⁻¹	0.004
PS	0.005	0.007	0.008

Fig. 1. Error-factors for the five astrometric parameters for 3 years of revolving scanning with $K = 270^\circ/\zeta$.

Appendix 3

The computing effort for the reductions of an RS system

A trivial but important aspect on the space astrometry project is that the necessary reductions can be carried out without unreasonable demands for computing time and storage capacity. Problems involving solution of very large and sparse systems of equations are certainly not unique to this project but arise in many branches of science and technology, e.g. in linear programming, structural analysis, electrical network analysis, genetics, photogrammetry, and photographic astrometry. Some of these problems are even structurally very similar to our problem and we may have much to learn from the experiences gained in these areas

de Vegt and Ebner (Mon. Not. R. astr. Soc. 167, 169, 1974) have described an efficient algorithm for the solution of large symmetric banded-bordered systems of equations encountered in blockadjustment methods in photographic astrometry. They give the following estimate of the computing time with a CDC 7600 computer:

$$t = 0.2 \cdot 10^{-9} (nm^2/2 + nm + 2nm + nl) \quad (\text{hr}) \quad (\text{A3.1})$$

n is the number of unknowns, m is the bandwidth and l the borderwidth. The storage capacity needed is approximately

$$n_s = n(m + 1) \quad (\text{words}) \quad (\text{A3.2})$$

We can apply these estimates to the minimum problem, which is to set up a sphere from observations of 40 000 RS stars during 2.5 years (13 800 orbits).

Suppose first that we attempt a solution in one stroke, i.e. without using the three-step procedure described in Appendix 1. Then n = 200 000. Optimal ordering can hardly bring down m and l below ~1000. Hence t = 60 hr and n_s = 400 M words.

Assuming that p consecutive orbits form one group in the three-step procedure, we have:

- step 1 n = 300 + 64p, m = 6 + 2p (?), l = 6.
 Solution repeated 13800/p times.
- step 2 n = m = 13800/p, l = 0. Only one solution.
- step 3 n = m = 5, l = 0. 40 000 solutions.

Results are given in the Table below. The computing time in step 3 is insignificant (0.001 h) and independent of p.

Computing times and storage capacities needed for the solutions in step 1 and 2

p	t_1	t_2	total time	n_{s1}	n_{s2}
1	13800 x 0.03 s = 0.10 h	260 h	260 h	5 k	190 M
5	2760 x 0.12 s = 0.09 h	2.1 h	2.2 h	14 k	8 M
10	1380 x 0.37 s = 0.14 h	0.26 h	0.40 h	30 k	2 M
15	920 x 0.85 s = 0.22 h	0.08 h	0.30 h	50 k	900 k
20	690 x 1.6 s = 0.31 h	0.03 h	0.34 h	80 k	500 k

Notes

1. The bandwidth in step 1 is very uncertain.
2. The times given are for the solution of the systems only. In practice, significant computing time is needed for computing the coefficients of the equations, and for input/output buffering of data since only a small portion of the data needed for computing the coefficients can be stored in the core memory.
3. The time estimates depend rather critically on assumptions concerning bandwidth etc. (and of course of the type of computer to be used), but the relative times, and hence the optimum choice for p (about 10 to 20), are fairly insensitive in this respect.